

Sub-ppm determination of thallium(I) in biological and complex materials

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Leucocrystal violet has been used as a chromogenic reagent for the determination of thallium(I) in biological and industrial effluent. The methodology involves the oxidation of Tl^I to Tl^{III} with bromine water and the resulting Tl^{III} liberating iodine from potassium iodide in acidic medium. The liberated iodine reacts with leucocrystal violet to form crystal violet dye, which is measured at 590 nm. In aqueous medium, the system obeys Beer's law in the range 2–20 μg per 25 ml (0.08–0.8 ppm) while in extraction medium the range is 0.5–5 μg per 100 ml (0.005–0.05 ppm). The apparent molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are found to be $2.21 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.00092 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

Thallium(I) is more toxic than thallium(III)¹. Various analytical methods, viz. AAS², GC³, HPLC⁴, ion selective electrode⁵, TLC⁶, laser induced fluorescence⁷, fluorimetry⁸, titrimetry⁹ are reported in the literature for direct determination of thallium. Several basic dyes are reported for the spectrophotometric determination of thallium(III), such as brilliant green, crystal violet, methyl violet, rhodamine B and methylene green and blue¹⁰. Here a new method for the determination of thallium(I) with leucocrystal violet (LCV) is described. The method involves the oxidation of thallium(I) to thallium(III), which liberates iodine from potassium iodide, and the liberated iodine reacts with LCV. The resultant dye is measured at 590 nm. The dye formed can also be extracted in isoamyl alcohol, which increases the sensitivity of the method. The method has been applied to the determination of thallium(I) in biological and industrial samples.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the crystal violet dye obtained in the proposed reaction showed maximum absorbance at 590 nm in aqueous and extraction medium. The reagent blank gave negligible absorbance at this wavelength. Beer's law was obeyed over the concentration range 2–20 μg per 25 ml (0.08–0.8 ppm) in aqueous medium, while in extraction medium the range was 0.5–5.0 μg per 100 ml (0.005–0.05 ppm). The molar absorptivity in aqueous medium and extracted medium were found to be 2.21×10^5 and $35.39 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The Sandell's sensitivity was $0.00092 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Under the proposed reaction condition, 0.5 ml of bromine water, 1 ml of 0.1% potassium iodide, 1 ml of LCV, 1M sodium hydroxide were required. For the removal of excess bromine, 1–2 drops of formic acid were sufficient.

The colour development was carried out at 40–45°, and it required ~25 min for completion of the reaction. At lower and higher temperature the colour intensity gradually faded. The final absorbance was measured at pH 3.5–4.0. Above pH 4.0, stability and sensitivity of the colour were severely affected. The colour development did not take place below pH 3.5. The extract was stable for several days under optimum conditions.

Precision of the method was verified by analyzing 10 μg of Tl^I per 25 ml of the final solution for a period of 7 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation of absorbance value were found to be ± 0.0098 and 2.26%, respectively, for seven replicate analysis. The standard deviation values of several readings such as 10, 12, 14 and 16 μg of Tl^I per 25 ml under the same conditions and during same period were ± 0.0098 , 0.00976, 0.00978 and 0.00977, respectively.

The tolerance limits (in ppm) of various ions were found to be as follows: La^{III} , Se^{IV} , Zr^{IV} (7050); Sn^{IV} , Cu^{II} , AsO_4^{3-} , PO_4^{3-} , NO_2^- (4950); Sb^{III} (4050); Co^{II} , Pb^{II} (2550); Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} (950); citrate (300). Most of the common ions did not interfere. As^V and Se^{IV} which also liberate iodine under similar conditions, interfered. Sn^{II} , Hg^{II} , Fe^{III} , nitrate and citrate interfere strongly in most of the other reported methods¹¹ but did not interfere in this method.

Experimental

A Systronic 106 spectrophotometer and a Systronic 335 pH meter were used. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled deionized water was used throughout. Standard thallium (B.D.H.) solution was prepared by dissolving thallium nitrate (100 mg) in water containing 1–2 drop of concentrated nitric acid and diluted to 100 ml with wa-

Table 1. Comparison with other spectrophotometric methods

Reagent	Medium/pH	λ_{\max} nm	Beer's law range (ppm)	Remarks
Brilliant-Green ^a	4 M HCl	640	0.2–2.0	Sn ^{II} , Hg ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , NO ₃ ⁻ and citrate interfere
Crystal-violet ^a	0.05 M HCl	595	0.4–2.4	Sn ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , Sb ^{III} , NO ₃ ⁻ citrate interfere
Methyl-violet ^a	0.18–0.2 M HCl	605	0.4–2.8	Sb ^{III} , Hg ^{II} , Fe ^{III} , citrate interfere
Rhodamine-B ^a	2 M HCl	555	0.4–2.8	Sn ^{II} , Sb ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , NO ₃ ⁻ interfere
Methylene green and blue ^a	0.15–0.2 M HCl	650	0.4–2.8	Sb ^{III} , Fe ^{III} , Ag ^I , NO ₃ ⁻ interfere
Present method	3.5–4.5 pH	590	0.08–0.8	Extractive, more sensitive and no interference from common cations and anions

^aRef. 10.

ter; working standards were prepared by dilution of this solution¹⁰. A saturated solution of bromine in water, a 50% aqueous formic acid and a 0.1% aqueous KI solution were prepared.

Leucocrystal violet (LCV, Eastman Kodak; 0.025 g) was dissolved in a mixture of water (20 ml) and 85% phosphoric acid (0.3 ml) and then diluted to 100 ml with water. This colourless solution was stable for several days.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing of 2–20 μg Tl^I, bromine water (0.5 ml) was added and shaken gently. The excess Br₂ was removed by adding 1–2 drops of formic acid. To it solutions of 0.1% KI (1 ml) and LCV (1 ml) were added. pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.5–4.0 with 1 M NaOH. The contents were then kept on a water-bath for 2–3 min/ at 40–45°. The time required was 20–25 min for complete colour development of the final solution. It was then extracted with isoamyl alcohol (2 × 5 ml). The absorbance of the violet extract was measured at 590 nm against a reagent blank.

Application : To assess the applicability of the method to biological samples, known amounts of thallium was added to urine and deproteinized blood samples¹². They were then analyzed for thallium by the present and reported¹¹ methods. The recovery range was found to be 95.6–98.5%. Industrial effluent sample (5 ml), taken from a near by steel plant was filtered and analyzed for thallium by the present and reported¹¹ methods. The recovery range was found to be 95.7–98.4%.

Known amount of thallium was added to natural water sample (5 ml) and analyzed by the present and reported¹¹

methods. The recovery range was found to be 96.8–98.6%. The flue dust samples (5 g), taken from acid plant of steel industry, was digested with acid mixture (10 ml HCl : HNO₃, 3 : 2 v/v)¹³ and evaporated under vacuum to 2 ml and diluted to 25 ml with water. The aliquot (5 ml) of the solution was analyzed for thallium by present and reported¹¹ methods. The recovery range was found to be 96.9–99.1%.

Conclusion : The results of determination of thallium(I) in biological and industrial samples are in agreement with those obtained with reported method¹¹. The present method for the determination of thallium is rapid, simple, sensitive and selective, and avoids use of hazardous chemicals. This method can be compared favorably with most of the other reported methods (Table 1). The method is fairly reproducible and has been successfully applied in biological and industrial samples.

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